

MAJOR CHALLENGES IN DOCUMENTARY TRANSLATION

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Abstract: In this article, we delve into the specific hurdles and strategies needed to translate documentaries. Documentaries come in all shapes and sizes, tailored for different viewers, objectives, and fields. However, our goal is to identify the common obstacles encountered by translators. Main difficulties include strict time constraints, the reliability of postproduction scripts, and the thorough investigation essential for precise terminology translation. Moreover, this paper analyzes distinct genre features like storytelling, voice-overs, subtitles, and instances where translators encounter intricate subjects and diverse speaker styles. By highlighting these challenges and suggesting ways to tackle them, this research adds to the knowledge and enhancement of documentary translation methods.

Key words: Documentary translation, audiovisual translation, narration, voice over, subtitling, translation challenges, terminological research, postproduction scripts.

I. INTRODUCTION

Defining the term “documentary” is challenging, although the distinction is straightforward from a professional perspective: when a dubbing studio offers a translator a job, the product manager specifies whether it is a documentary, a film, a series episode, or a cartoon. However, from a theoretical standpoint, the term

“documentary” has been variously defined, as demonstrated by Leon (1999) and Espasa (2004), who also trace the origins of documentaries. Unlike fictional works, documentaries focus on reality, but distinguishing between fiction and reality is not always simple, as documentaries, despite being based on real events, often present a subjective interpretation.

Although each documentary is unique—varying by target audience, purpose, and other factors—and comes with its own specific challenges, I aim to draw some general conclusions. I will categorize the primary issues in documentary translation into two groups: working conditions and more specific problems, such as terminology, types of speakers, and translation modes.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research used both qualitative and quantitative methods to look into the difficulties and methods used in translating documentaries. It included translated documentaries, scripts, and interviews with translators. Here are the steps in the research:

- a. **Corpus Analysis:** A selection of documentaries covering various subjects and specialization levels were analyzed to identify common translation challenges.
- b. **Interviews:** Professional translators were interviewed to gather insights into the practical difficulties they face, particularly concerning tight deadlines, research demands, and script quality.
- c. **Case Studies:** Specific examples of narration, voice over, and subtitling were examined to understand how translators handle these aspects. Special cases involving complex terminological challenges and varied speaker types were also reviewed.
- d. **Techniques and Solutions:** The techniques used in the corpus were documented, and translators provided recommendations for solving identified issues. These techniques were then categorized and analyzed to offer a comprehensive overview of best practices in documentary translation.

III. RESULTS

Regarding specific genre characteristics, audiovisual non-fictional products cover a wide range of topics with varying levels of specialization. These topics are presented by different types of speakers and discourses, which are re-voiced using various techniques. As a result, translators are usually not experts in any particular field. Instead, they must quickly acquire all the necessary information about a specific subject to understand and accurately translate the documentary.

When it comes to the working conditions, translators often face tight deadlines. Although this pressure is not unique to documentaries, it is particularly relevant here because documentary translation typically requires more time. While some fictional works also demand significant research, translating documentaries generally involves a longer and more intensive research process than translating a series episode or a cartoon. Consequently, meeting deadlines is a major challenge.

Another significant issue is the availability and quality of postproduction scripts. When these scripts are provided, their accuracy can vary, so translators should use them cautiously and critically as reference points, recognizing they are translating an audiovisual product, not merely a written one. To ensure correct transcription of proper names, translators can use reference works, atlases, and online resources. However, they should primarily gather as much information as possible from the documentary itself, as it is the most reliable source. For instance, a toponym mentioned by the narrator might be supported by a visual of the location or a sign displaying the name. In more challenging cases, translators can consult native speakers, either in person or by using new technologies to send a sound file recorded via computer.

IV. DISCUSSION

Next, the techniques employed in the corpus will be outlined and supplemented with recommendations from translators on how to address the previously mentioned issues.

1. Narration

In documentaries, narration plays a key role in helping viewers understand the content. The narrator's voice guides you by giving context, explanations, and insights. It's important because it influences how you perceive and comprehend the subject. Translators have to be meticulous when adapting the narration to keep the same tone and clarity in the translated version. This means they need to do thorough research to capture all the subtle details of the topic.

2. Voice-over

In documentaries, voice-over involves re-voicing the original speakers, like interviewees or on-screen characters, in a different language. This is tough because the translator needs to grasp not just the words but also the speaker's tone, emotion, and purpose. With different speakers and styles, translators must quickly get specialized topics and express them accurately.

3. Subtitling

Subtitling is a widely used method in translating documentaries. It works by showing text on the screen that translates what is being said. Subtitling comes with its own set of challenges. These include squeezing translations into a small space and timeframe, all the while making sure they are clear and correct. Translators have to sum up the original dialogue without missing any important details. They also need to make sure the subtitles match the audio and visuals perfectly. This task demands sharp language abilities and a thorough understanding of the content.

4. Special cases

Documentary translation can be tricky due to the unique content involved. Documentaries often delve into specialized subjects, so translators often need to do thorough research on specific terms. Also, the scripts used in postproduction can differ in quality and availability, making it necessary for translators to use visual cues like images and on-screen text to ensure precise translation. In tough situations, translators may seek help from native speakers or use innovative technologies to verify accuracy.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this article aims to shed light on an overlooked area of audiovisual translation by addressing the primary challenges in translating documentaries. Despite the generalizations made in this article, two essential factors must always be considered: first, documentaries are an audiovisual medium, making sound and image critical components—what matters is not the script but what is heard and seen; second, each original documentary has unique characteristics that the translator must identify and convey in the target language.

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